

On the Triple Nitrites of the Rare Earths and a New Micro-test for Cæsium.

BY HARISH CHANDRA GOSWAMI AND PULIN BIHARI SARKAR.

The ingenious method of isolation of spectroscopically pure europium, gadolinium and terbium effected by Prof. Urbain by the use of Bi "comme élément séparateur" is based on the isodimorphism of hydrated bismuth nitrates with the rare-earth nitrates and the isomorphism of the double nitrates of bismuth of the type $2M_1(NO_3)_3 \cdot 3M_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 24H_2O$ where M_1 may be Bi or Σ La up to Ga, and M_2 may be Mg, Zn, Ni, Co or Mn.

Ball and Abram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 2110) prepared a number of complex bismuthinitrites of the types $X_3Bi(NO_2)_6$ and $X_2YBi(NO_2)_6$ where X stands for NH_4 , K, Rb, Cs and Tl, and Y for Li, Na or Ag.

Our knowledge of the nitrites of the rare-earths is extremely meagre. This led the authors to investigate whether cerium and other rare-earth elements form triple nitrites analogous to those of bismuth. The following triple nitrites of the formula $Cs_2NaR(NO_2)_6$ (where $R=Ce, La, Pr, Na, Sm$ or Gd) have been prepared and described in the paper. The elements of the yttrium group beyond gadolinium do not form such nitrites. These are sparingly soluble octahedral crystals stable at the ordinary temperature. Their aqueous solutions are slowly hydrolysed. The formation of these octahedral triple salts may be used for the micro-detection of cæsium. The test appears to be specific for Cs since potassium and rubidium do not respond.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cæsium-sodium-cerium nitrite—Cerous nitrate solution (50%, 10 c.c.) was mixed with sodium nitrite solution (50%, 10 c.c.) and the mixture was filtered. To the filtrate, 10 c.c. of a cæsium nitrate solution (10%) were then stirred in and the solution kept in a stoppered bottle. After 4 hours, the yellow crystals were drained, washed, first with a sodium nitrite solution (10%), then with a mixture of acetone

and water and finally with acetone. They were then dried in a desiccator. The salt is stable in air at the ordinary temperature but decomposes gradually when heated to 100°. [Found: N, 11·98; Cs, 37·70; Ce, 20·06; Na, 3·29. $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaCe}(\text{NO}_2)_6$ requires N, 11·90; Cs, 37·70; Ce, 19·88; Na, 3·26 per cent].

Cæsium-sodium-lanthanum nitrite.—The method of preparation is similar to that of the preceding salt. [Found: Cs, 37·78; La, 20·0; Na, 3·2. $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaLa}(\text{NO}_2)_6$ requires Cs, 37·77; La, 19·74; Na, 3·27 per cent].

Cæsium-sodium-praseodymium nitrite.—The method of preparation is similar to above. The triple salt was obtained in the form of pale green octahedral crystals. [Found: Cs, 37·89; Na, 3·15; Pr, 20·0. $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaPr}(\text{NO}_2)_6$ requires Cs, 37·66; Na, 3·26; Pr, 19·96 per cent].

Cæsium-sodium-neodymium nitrite was separated exactly as the previous one. [Found: Cs, 37·65; Na, 3·05; Nd, 20·21. $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaNd}(\text{NO}_2)_6$ requires Cs, 37·49; Na, 3·24; Nd, 20·35 per cent].

Cæsium-sodium-samarium nitrite was prepared exactly as praseodymium and neodymium salts. [Found: Cs, 37·4; Na, 3·16; Sm, 21·29. $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaSm}(\text{NO}_2)_6$ requires Cs, 37·16; Na, 3·21; Sm, 21·03 per cent].

Cæsium-sodium-gadolinium nitrite was prepared as the preceding ones. [Found: Cs, 36·70; Gd, 21·69; Na, 3·18. $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaGd}(\text{NO}_2)_6$ requires Cs, 36·80; Gd, 21·78; Na, 3·16 per cent].

Method of analysis.—The salts were decomposed with concentrated HCl and the rare-earths were precipitated as hydroxides by double precipitation with ammonia. The precipitated hydroxides were filtered, dissolved in dilute HNO_3 and precipitated as oxalates. They were then ignited and weighed as oxides. From the filtrate ammonium salts were removed and the total alkali metals were weighed in the form of sulphates. Sodium was estimated as sodium-magnesium-uranyl acetate and cæsium was determined by difference. Nitrogen was estimated by conversion to ammonia by distillation with zinc and alkali and subsequent absorption in standard acids.

Micro-detection of cæsium.—All the triple nitrites described in this paper furnished a ready method for the micro-detection of cæsium. The praseodymium salt appears to be best suited for the purpose since it is the most stable of the series.

Reagent.—3 G. of praseodymium nitrate and 10 g. of sodium nitrite were dissolved in 100 c.c. of water. The solution was then filtered and preserved in a well-stoppered bottle.

Procedure.—A drop of the reagent was taken on a microscope slide and was touched with a small platinum loop dipped in a solution of caesium nitrate. After 3 or 4 minutes, beautiful octahedral crystals appear when viewed through a microscope (magnification 400 times). The limit of identification has been measured to be 4×10^{-8} g. (0.04 γ). The test is specific for caesium, rubidium and potassium do not interfere. It appears to be more sensitive than the triple caesium-silver-gold chloride test advocated by Emich. It is advisable to use the alkali (caesium) salt in the form of a nitrate.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received August 13, 1935.

Condensation of Cotarnine and *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde.

BY K. N. KAUL AND G. S. AHLUWALIA.

Ahluwalia, Kaul and Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 197) have condensed cotarnine with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and formulated the product as *o*-nitrobenzoylhydrocotarnine following Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1458). A later note of Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 840), in which this formulation has been modified, escaped our attention. The analytical values for nitrogen come within experimental error whether $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3$ or $C_{19}H_{18}O_6N_2$ is accepted. A carbon hydrogen determination was considered unnecessary because it was not realised that there could be anything wrong with Robinson and Robinson's formulation.

Our attention has been drawn to this later note of Robinson and Robinson. Therefore we desire to correct our formulation of the condensation product and bring it in line with the later formula of these authors.

In fact we stated that "following Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1458) the compound was formulated as I" (*loc. cit.*).

UNIVERSITY CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF THE PUNJAB, LAHORE.

Received May 29, 1935.